

FATIGUE FACE DETECTION USING DEEP LEARNING: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT:

Driver drowsiness is a significant factor contributing to road accidents worldwide. Detecting drowsiness in drivers is crucial for preventing accidents and ensuring road safety. In this study, we propose a comprehensive experiment utilizing 7 different CNN models based on transfer learning for driver drowsiness detection. The models considered include VGG16, VGG19, Mobile Net, ResNet50, Alex Net, Google Net, and Dense Net. The experiments are conducted using the yawn eye dataset, which is specifically curate for driver drowsiness detection tasks. Our research focuses on driver drowsiness detection, which entails identifying drowsiness by analyzing the driver's face, particularly focusing on the eyes and mouth. The system, trained on a dataset, detects instances where the driver's eyes are closed and detects yawning, triggering an alarm to alert the driver. The performance of each deep learning model is evaluated. The results reveal that VGG16 achieves the highest accuracy of 98.4%, precision of 99%, recall of 96%, and f1 score of 98%. Notably VGG16 emerges as the best-performing model for driver drowsiness detection among the tested architectures.

Keywords: CNN, Driver Drowsiness Detection, Deep Learning Models, Road Safety, Transfer Learning, VGG16

I.INTRODUCTION:

Drowsiness refers to sleepiness. The drowsiness might also additionally ultimate for a couple of minutes however its consequences can be disastrous. The main cause of sleepiness is typically exhaustion, which reduces alertness and attention, although other causes include lack of concentration, medications, sleep issues, drinking alcohol, or shift work. They are unable to predict when sleep may strike. Even though falling asleep while driving is dangerous, being tired makes it difficult to drive safely even when you are awake. One in twenty drivers is said to have fallen asleep behind the wheel. The most at risk for tired driving is truck and bus drivers with commutes of 10 to 12 hours. These people endanger other drivers more than they endanger themselves. Driving a long distance while sleep deprived might make you drowsy, as can driving when you need to sleep. In these scenarios, the driver's drowsiness has developed and is to blame for any accidents that occur on road. According to National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA), the police and hospital reports identified that 100,000 car accidents and over 1,500 deaths were caused due to drowsiness of drivers each year.

Drowsy driving is thought to be responsible for approximately 1,550 fatalities, 71,000 injuries, and \$12.5 billion in financial losses. A sleepy driver was a factor in 697 fatalities in 2019. NHTSA acknowledges that it is challenging to quantify the precise number of accidents, or

fatalities caused by drowsy driving and that the reported figures are underestimates. Fortunately, it is now possible to recognize tiredness in a motorist and warn them before a collision. Drivers who are drowsy exhibit a variety of symptoms, such as frequent yawning, closed eyes for an extended period of time, and erratic lane changes. In recent years, methods for identifying driver drowsiness detection (DDD) have been effectively researched. To prevent accidents, researchers have suggested a variety of ways to identify tiredness as soon as feasible.

In our effort, detecting drowsiness begins with the identification of a face, followed by the identification of an eye's position and pattern of blinking. A "Shape predictor including 68 landmarks" is used to analyze faces. We utilize a camera most likely a webcam in this instance positioned in the direction of the driver's face to identify the driver's face and his or her facial landmarks in order to estimate the position of the driver's eye. To do this, it must use in-house image processing to examine every face and set of eyes. When the system locates the position of the eyes, it next determines whether they are open or closed and the blinking rate, which is how quickly the eyes are closing and opening. The alarm will sound, warning the driver, after a predetermined amount of time with the eyes closed. We begin with a score of zero for the eye open or closed; if the eye is closed, the score will rise, and if it is open, the score will fall. If the score exceeds a limit, then the alarm will ring to alert driver. The remaining sections of this paper are structured as follows: Literature review, Dataset, methodology, experimental result discussion, references.

II.LITERATURE REVIEW:

Many researchers have attempted various technologies such as monitoring of underlying patterns in steering, monitoring vehicle position in lane, monitoring the eye/face of the driver, physiological measurement etc. In this literature review, we will summarize some of the recent and relevant research papers on these topics.

1. Based on Convolutional Neural Network:

Xiaolei Li.et.al [1] proposed a Computer vision-based framework with personalization threshold and multi-feature fusion for driver fatigue detection using Convolutional Neural Network. MobileNetV3 is used in this technique. In this technique transfer learning is employed to train the eye and mouth state classifier. Here they used NTHU-DDD dataset. In this technique they obtained 92.21% of accuracy.

Abid Ali Minhas.et.al [2] proposed a smart analysis of driver fatigue and drowsiness using Convolutional Neural Network. Here detection is done using state-of-the-art CNN models such as Inception V3, VGG16 and ResNet50. ResNet 50 model has the best accuracy as compared to all other deep learning models. In this technique they obtained 93.6% of accuracy.

Zuopeng Zhao.et.al [3] proposed a driver fatigue detection based on CNN using EM-CNN. In the proposed algorithm, the (MTCNN) architecture is employed in face detection and feature point location and the ROI is extracted using feature points. EM-CNN is proposed to detect the states of the eyes and mouth from ROI images. PERCLOS and POM are two parameters used for

fatigue detection. Here several other CNN methods are implemented to improve the accuracy. I.e. Alex Net, Google Net, ResNet. Here they obtained accuracy is 93.64%.

Mohit Dua.et.al [4] proposed a deep CNN models based ensemble approach to driver drowsiness detection. The proposed architecture consists of four deep learning models: Alex Net, VGG-Face Net, Flow image Net and ResNet. Also, these models consider four types of different features such as hand gestures, facial expressions, behavioral features and head movements for the implementation. Here NTHU-DDD dataset is used in this technique. The accuracy obtained from this system came out to be 85%.

Ming-Zhou Liu et.al [5] proposed a new method for real-time driver fatigue detection using Convolutional Neural Network and Long Short-Term Memory (CNN-LSTM). The proposed method uses a simple linear clustering algorithm (SLIC) to divide the driver's image into super pixels of uniform size, which are used as input of CNN. By using the RD-CNN with simple structure trained in this paper, the mouth and eye regions can be accurately segmented from the SLIC image. Experimental data shows that this method can not only overcome the influence of illumination, background, angle and individual differences. In this technique vehicle camera (DF-806 6) is used. Here the accuracy of detection can reach 96.78%.

2. Based on Deep Learning:

Dohun Kim.et.al [6] proposed a Real-time driver monitoring system (DMS) with facial landmark based eye closure detection and head pose recognition using deep learning. They utilized an infrared (IR) camera to capture and analyze video data and they used YOLO V7 algorithm. Here camera has some features such as IRLED control functionality and seam less communication between the camera and the ECU. In this technique IR-datasets are used to improve its performance. In this technique they obtained accuracy is 95.1%.

Ajinkya Rajkar.et.al [7] proposed a Driver drowsiness detection using deep learning. The paper examines the most commonly used techniques for detecting driver drowsiness, such as physiological measures, eye-tracking, and machine learning approaches. The authors also discuss the challenges faced by these systems and the future trends in the field. Open CV's Haar cascade algorithm is used to see the driver's face and eye region. They used the Closed Eye in the Wild dataset (CEW) and Yawning Detection Dataset (YawDD) In this technique they obtained 96% accuracy.

Fan Liu.et.al [8] proposed **driver fatigue detection and its advances on the use of RGB-D camera and deep learning**. The paper analyzes and discusses four types of different fatigue detection technologies based on driver physiological signals, behavior features, vehicle running features, and information fusion, respectively. Then, it focuses on RGB-D camera and deep learning which are two state-of-the-art solutions in this field. The paper presents the work on integration of RGB-D camera and deep learning, where Generative Adversarial Networks and multi-channel schemes are utilized to enhance the performance. In this technique they obtained 90.1% of accuracy.

Israt Jahan.et.al [9] proposed a **real-time driver drowsiness detector using deep learning named 4D**. The paper reviews some of the existing deep learning methods for eye state detection, such as Alex Net, VGG Net, Res Net, and Inception. The paper also compares the performance of two pre-trained models, VGG16, VGG19 and 4D models. Which are widely used for image classification tasks, on the MRL Eye dataset. However, the paper argues that VGG16 and VGG19 are not suitable for real-time applications, as they have a large number of parameters and layers; the paper concludes that the proposed 4D model is efficient for eye state detection. The paper also suggests some future directions for improving the proposed system, such as incorporating other behavioral signals. Here the obtained accuracy is 97.06%.

Vijay kumar.et.al [10] proposed a **driver drowsiness detection using modified deep learning architecture**. The paper proposes a non-invasive approach to detect driver drowsiness using facial features. Here the mouth and eye regions are extracted from the video frame and applied on a hybrid deep learning model for drowsiness detection. The proposed hybrid model is compared with convolutional neural network, InceptionV3, and LSTM over NTHU-DDD dataset. The proposed model performs better than the other models in terms of performance measures. In this technique they obtained 82% of accuracy.

3. Based on Image Processing:

T.Vesselenyi.et.al [11] proposed a **driver drowsiness detection using ANN image processing**. Here three types of methods are developed: EEG and EOG signal processing and driver image analysis. In this paper, the authors focus on the possibility of detecting the drowsy or alert state of the driver based on the images taken during driving and by analyzing the state of the driver's eyes: opened, half-opened, and closed. For this purpose, two kinds of artificial neural networks were employed: a 1 hidden layer network and an auto encoder network. The proposed hybrid model was compared with other models over NTHU-DDD dataset and was found to perform better in terms of performance measures. In this technique they obtained positive classification results.

Burcu kir savas.et.al [12] proposed a **real time driver fatigue detection system based on Multi-Task ConNN**. The authors propose a non-invasive approach to detect driver fatigue in real-time using facial features. The proposed model is based on a Multi-tasking Convolutional Neural Network (ConNN*) model that utilizes eye and mouth characteristics for driver's behavior model. The proposed model is capable of detecting driver fatigue by calculating eyes' closure duration/Percentage of eye closure (PERCLOS) and yawning frequency/frequency of mouth (FOM). In this study, the fatigue degree of the driver is divided into 3 classes. The proposed model achieved 96% fatigue detection on YawDD and NthuDDD dataset .

Naveen Senniappan Karuppusamy.et.al [13] proposed a **Multimodal system to detect driver fatigue using EEG, Gyroscope, and Image Processing**. The authors propose a neural network-based hybrid multimodal system that detects driver fatigue using electroencephalography (EEG) data, gyroscope data, and image processing data. The proposed system is capable of detecting driver fatigue by calculating the power spectral density (PSD) of EEG signals, the angular velocity of the gyroscope, and the eye closure duration. The proposed model was tested on a dataset of 20 subjects and achieved an accuracy of 94.5%.

Mohsen Poursadeghiyan.et.al [14] proposed **Driver drowsiness detection using Image Processing**. The study was conducted on five suburban drivers using a driving simulator based on virtual reality laboratory of Khaje-Nasir Toosi University of Technology in Tehran, Iran. The facial expressions, as well as location of the eyes, were detected by Viola-Jones algorithm. Criteria for detecting drivers' levels of drowsiness by eyes tracking included eye blink duration blink frequency, and PERCLOS. The results showed several dynamic changes of the eyes during the periods of drowsiness. The present study proposes a fast and accurate method for detecting the levels of drivers' drowsiness by considering the dynamic changes of the eyes. Here obtained accuracy is 93%.

Qianyang Zhuang.et.al [15] proposed a **Driver fatigue detection method based on eye states with pupil and iris segmentation**. A streamlined network, consisting of a segmentation network and a decision network, is designed, which greatly improves the accuracy and generalization of eye openness estimation. Specifically, the segmentation network that uses light U-Net structure performs a pixel-level classification on the eye images, which can accurately extract pupil and iris features from the video's images. Then, the extracted feature map is used to guide the decision network to estimate eye openness. Finally, the detection method is tested by the National Tsing Hua University Drowsy Driver Detection (NTHU-DDD) Video Dataset and the precision of fatigue detection achieves 93.72%.

Based on deep learning:

S.No.	Method	Author	Algorithm	Dataset	Accuracy
1.	Real-time driver monitoring system with facial landmark based eye closure detection and head pose recognition.	Dohun Kim	Yolo V7	IR Camera	95.1%
2.	Driver drowsiness detection.	Ajinkya Rajkar	Open Cv's Haar Cascade algorithm	CEW and YawDD	96%
3.	Driver fatigue detection and its advances on the use of RGB-D camera	Fan Liu	General Adversarial networks and multi-channel schemes	RGB-D camera	90.1%
4.	4D: Real time driver drowsiness detector	Israt Jahan	Alex Net,VGG Net Res Net,Inception	MRL eye dataset	97.53%
5.	Driver drowsiness detection	Vijay Kumar	Inception V3 and LSTM (long short-term memory).	NTHU-DDD	82%

Based on CNN:

S.No.	Method	Author	Algorithm	Dataset	Accuracy
1.	Computer vision-based framework with personalization threshold and multi-feature fusion.	Xiao Lei	MobileNetV3	NTHU-DDD	92.21%
2.	Smart analysis of driver fatigue detection.	Abid Ali Minhas	InceptionV3, VGG16, ResNet50.	Sleepy and active human face images dataset	93.6%
3.	Driver fatigue detection based on CNN using EM-CNN	Zuopeng Zhao	Alex Net, Google Net, ResNet.	MTCNN and EM-CNN	93.64%
4.	Deep CNN models based ensemble approach to driver drowsiness detection.	Mohit Dua	Alex Net, VGG-Face Net, ResNet, Flow image net.	NTHU-DDD	85%
5.	Real-time driver fatigue detection using (CNN-LSTM)_	Ming-Zhou	RD-CNN, SLIC	Vehicle camera (DF-806 6)	96.78%

Based on Image processing:

S.NO.	Method	Author	Algorithm	Dataset	Accuracy
1.	Driver drowsiness detection using ANN image processing	T.Vesselenyi	EEG and EOG signals	NTHU-DDD	-
2.	Real time driver fatigue detection	Burcu Kir Savas	Multi-task ConNN	YawDD and NthuDD	96%
3.	Multimodal system to detect driver fatigue	Naveen senniappan karuppusamy	EEG and Gyroscope	CWT Tagged dataset	94.5%
4.	Driver drowsiness detection	Mohsen poursadeghiyan	Violla-Jones	CCD Camera	93%
5.	Driver fatigue detection method based on eye states with pupil and iris segmentation	Qianyang Zhuang	U-Net structure	NTHU-DDD	96.72%

CONCLUSION:

Detecting driver sleepiness and drowsiness while driving is crucial for public health and road safety, aiming to prevent accidents. This study proposes a classification system based on transfer learning utilizing deep learning architectures. The dataset is classified into four classes: open-eye, closed-eye, no-yawn, and yawn. Experimental results using the VGG16 model demonstrate an impressive accuracy of 98.4% and an F1-score exceeding 95% for each class. These findings underscore the effectiveness of transfer learning-based tools in optimizing security measures.

REFERENCE:

- 1) Li, Xiao lei, et al. "Computer vision-based driver fatigue detection framework with personalization threshold and multi-feature fusion." *Signal, Image and Video Processing* (2023): 1-10.
- 2) Minhas, A.A., Jabbar, S., Farhan, M. *et al.* A smart analysis of driver fatigue and drowsiness detection using convolutional neural networks. *Multimed Tools Appl* **81**, 26969–26986 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-022-13193-4>
- 3) Zhao, Zuopeng, et al. "Driver fatigue detection based on convolutional neural networks using EM-CNN." *Computational intelligence and neuroscience* 2020 (2020).
- 4) Kim, Dohun, et al. "Real-time driver monitoring system with facial landmark-based eye closure detection and head pose recognition." *Scientific reports* 13.1 (2023): 18264.
- 5) Liu, Ming-Zhou, et al. "Real time detection of driver fatigue based on CNN-LSTM." *IET Image Processing* 16.2 (2022): 576-595.
- 6) Dua, Mohit, et al. "Deep CNN models-based ensemble approach to driver drowsiness detection." *Neural Computing and Applications* 33 (2021): 3155-3168.
- 7) Rajkar, Ajinkya, Nilima Kulkarni, and Aniket Raut. "Driver drowsiness detection using deep learning." *Applied Information Processing Systems: Proceedings of ICCET 2021*. Springer Singapore, 2022.
- 8) Liu, Fan, et al. "A review of driver fatigue detection and its advances on the use of RGB-D camera and deep learning." *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 116 (2022): 105399.
- 9) Jahan, Israt, et al. "4D: a real-time driver drowsiness detector using deep learning." *Electronics* 12.1 (2023): 235.
- 10) Kumar, Vijay, Shivam Sharma, and Ranjeet. "Driver drowsiness detection using modified deep learning architecture." *Evolutionary Intelligence* 16.6 (2023): 1907-1916.
- 11) Vesselenyi, Tiberiu, et al. "Driver drowsiness detection using ANN image processing." *IOP conference series: materials science and engineering*. Vol. 252. No. 1. IOP Publishing, 2017.

- 12) Kır Savaş, Burcu, and Yasar Becerikli. "Driver Fatigue Detection via Eye State Analyses Based on Deep Learning Approach." *The Proceedings of the International Conference on Smart City Applications*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022.
- 13) Karuppusamy, Naveen Senniappan, and Bo-Yeong Kang. "Multimodal system to detect driver fatigue using EEG, gyroscope, and image processing." *IEEE Access* 8 (2020): 129645-129667.
- 14) Poursadeghiyan, Mohsen, et al. "Using image processing in the proposed drowsiness detection system design." *Iranian journal of public health* 47.9 (2018): 1371.
- 15) Zhuang, Qianyang, et al. "Driver fatigue detection method based on eye states with pupil and iris segmentation." *Ieee Access* 8 (2020): 173440-173449.